

Prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension and its associated risk factors among healthcare workers of some selected hospitals in Dutse, Jigawa state, north western Nigeria

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Abstract

Hypertension remains a major global public health challenge as the leading risk factor for cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Annually, it accounts for 7.1 million (one-third) of global preventable premature death. The study was carried out to determine the prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension and associated risk factors among healthcare workers in Dutse, Jigawa state.

The study is a cross sectional in which 107 participants were recruited using convenient sampling technique. All the participants' blood pressure was measured using mercury sphygmomanometer and a stethoscope. Height and weight was measured and was used to calculate BMI. A data sheet was used to assess other risk factors of hypertension (age, gender, obesity, occupational stress, family history, physical activity level, dietary habits and smoking). The data obtained was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive (mean, standard deviation & percentage) and inferential (Pearson & Spearman) statistics were used to summarize the data. Alpha level was set at <0.05. All statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 16.0.

Out of 107 participants, 69(64.5%) were male and 38(35.5%) were female. the mean age of the participants was 32.8 ±7.54 years, SBP was 124 ±12.50 mm Hg, DBP was 79 ±10.54 mm Hg and BMI was 22.3 ±4.09 kg/m². About 30(28.0%) nurses participated, 25 (23.3%) of the participant were medical doctors, 16 (14.9%) are from medical laboratory scientist, 12(11.2%) are from radiographers, pharmacist and physiotherapist each. Prevalence of undiagnosed HTN was found to be 26.2% in the participants. Age, BMI, and physical activity level were found to be significantly associated with HTN (p < 0.05). On the other hand, occupational stress, family history of HTN, dietary habits and smoking showed no significant relationship (p > 0.05). A moderate prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension was found and hypertension is associated with age, BMI, and physical activity level. Therefore, physical activity and weight reduction programmes should be encouraged among health care workers, the need for services to detect and manage undiagnosed cases through regular blood pressure measurements is recommended.

Keywords: Undiagnosed Hypertension, Health care Workers, Hypertension

Introduction

Hypertension remains a major global public health challenge as the leading risk factor for cardiovascular morbidity and mortality [1] [2]. Annually, it accounts for 7.1 million (one-third) of global preventable premature deaths [2] [3] [4].

Diagnosis of hypertension is made by the observation of persistently high blood pressure, this needs accurate measurement of blood pressure on at least two different occasions, in each time the individual is given enough time to relax [5]. In very high blood pressure levels (SBP ≥160 mmHg and/or DBP ≥100 mmHg) with evidence of target-organ damage only one reading is necessary to start on treatment [6].

In the United States, essential hypertension has

An elevation of the systolic and/or diastolic blood pressure increases the risk of developing heart disease, kidney disease, arteriosclerosis, eye damage, and stroke [5]. These complications of hypertension are often referred to as end-organ damage because damage to these organs is the end result of chronic high blood pressure [6]. been associated with Family history of hypertension, advanced age, African-American race, obesity, inactivity, cigarette smoking, excessive salt intake and excessive alcohol intake [6]. A number of physical and psychological factors associated with individuals occupation can increase their risk of developing cardiovascular diseases, numerous studies carried out mainly in Europe and USA have shown a higher incidence of cardiovascular disease (CVD) in certain occupations such as swing shift, bus,

tractors and taxi drivers [6] [7].

A large numbers of people with hypertension are not aware they have this condition and highlight the need for targeted case finding to help manage undiagnosed hypertension and reduce future health damage. The national RoI data suggest that there are approximately five adults aged 45+ years with undiagnosed hypertension for every three adults aged 45+ years with clinically diagnosed hypertension [7].

Specifically on health care workers, various studies were conducted in different part of the world on general inclination of CVD risk factors among this occupational category[1] [3] [4] [5] [7] [8] [9]. In Havana, Cuba, cardiovascular disorders were found to be a significant health problem among health care workers, with hypertension having the highest incidence. It is unknown whether the several CVD risk factors especially hypertension that where observed among healthcare workers in certain parts of the world are also common among health care workers in Jigawa state, though healthcare workers are very critical, and effective in primary prevention of undiagnosed hypertension and its risk factors, there is tendency for them to ignore themselves.

This therefore, informed the formulation of the study which was aimed at determining the prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension and its risk factors among health care workers in Dutse, Jigawa state.

METHODOLOGY

The research was a cross sectional study, which was conducted to estimate the prevalence of the result of the interest for a given inhabitants that was conducted in Jigawa state, Nigeria. The population of this study comprised of all nurses, medical doctors, physiotherapist, pharmacist, Radiographers and medical laboratory scientist working in the Rasheed Shekoni Specialist Hospital(RSSH) and General Hospital Dutse (GHD) of Jigawa state.

Participants

A total of 107 participants were recruited for the study using convenient sampling technique. All serving healthcare worker in RSSH and GHD that have no history of hypertension were included in the study and pregnant women were excluded.

Procedure

Ethical approval was sought from ministry of health Dutse and RSSH, informed consent was given to the participants, and only those that signed participated in the study. The measurement of Blood pressure, weight and stature was taken, Body Mass index (BMI) was calculated. In addition Stress measuring Questionnaire (international stress management Association ISMA QUESTIONNAIRE) was used to measure the occupational stress while Global physical activity questionnaire was used to assess the physical activity level.

Risk factors of Hypertension were categorized and assessed:

(a) Age: - The age of participants was recorded in years. The age associated risk grouped as follows: [8].

(1) 19-49yrs = at no risk

(2) ?50yrs = at risk

(b) Obesity: - This was assessed using BMI values. BMI outcomes from 25 to 29 is considered overweight, with BMI outcomes equal to and greater than 30 indicative of obesity [9].The obesity associated risk was coded as:

0 = at no risk

1 = at risk

(c) Family history of HTN: - An individual having a family history of HTN was considered at "at risk" [10] and was coded as:

0 = at no risk

1 = at risk

(d) Smoking: - An individual who is currently a smoker or have ever smoked in his lifetime was considered at risk of HTN [11]. It was coded as:

0 = at no risk

1 = at risk

(e) Dietary habits: an individual with poor dietary habits was considered at risk of HTN [3]. And was coded as:

0 = at no risk

1 = at risk

(f) Occupational stress:- Occupational stress participant was considered at risk of developing HTN using ISMA questionnaire

0 = at no risk

1 = at risk

(g) Physical inactivity using Global physical activity questionnaire

1 = low physical activity = at risk

2= moderate at no risk

3= high at no risk

Data Analysis Procedure

The data obtained was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was used to summarize data using mean, median, standard deviation and percentage. Inferential statistics of Spearman and Pearson was used to determine relationship between BP and risk factors of HTN. P value of <0.05 was use to show significance relationship. All statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 16.0

Results

The study sample consisted of 107 healthcare workers 69(64.5%) were male and 38(35.5%) were female. The mean age of the participants was 32.8 years,this study found that majority of the participants fall within the middle age category and they are averagely normal weight individuals. The result also showed that the BP of the participants is in the safer range as shown in the table 1 below.

Table 1: Physical/anthropometric characteristics of participants

Variables	Mean± SD
Age (years)	32.28±7.54
W (Kg)	59.45±11.30
H (m)	1.64±.099
BMI (Kg/m ²)	22.31±4.09
SBP (mmHg)	123.89±12.50
DBP (mmHg)	78.29±10.54

Key: W= weight kg=kilogram H= height m=meters BMI= Body mass index SBP=systolic blood pressure DBP= diastolic blood pressure

About 30(28.0%) nurses participated, 25 (23.3%) of the participant are medical doctors,12 (11.2%) participants are physiotherapist,16(14.9%) are medical lab scientist,12(11.2%) are radiographers and 12(11.2%) are pharmacist the result are illustrated in the table 2 below.

Table: 2 frequency distribution of the occupational status of participants

Variables	n	%
NURSING	30	28.0
MEDICAL DOCTORS	25	23.3
PHYSIOTHERAPIST	12	11.2
MEDICAL LAB SCI	16	14.9
RADIOGRAPHERS	12	11.2
PHARMACISTS	12	11.2
TOTAL	107	100

Key: n= frequency %= percentage

Table: 3 Frequency distribution of Physical activity level of the participants

Variables	n	%
LOW	53	49.5
MODERATE	37	34.6
HIGH	17	15.9
TOTAL	107	100.0

Key: n= frequency %= percentage

The above table shows that 49.5% have low physical activity level, 34.6% moderate and 15% presented with high physical activity level

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of risk factors of HTN

Variables	n (%)	
	At no risk	At risk
FHXDM	92(86.0)	15(14)
FHXHTN	79 (73.8)	28 (26.2)
DIETARY HABITS	75 (70.1)	32 (29.9)
SMOKING	94 (87.9)	13

Key: Hx=history HTN=Hypertension DM =Diabetes

The table above describes some risk factors of hypertension with dietary habits being the highest followed by family history of hypertension.

Table 5: Hypertension status categories of the participants

Variables	n (%)
Hypertension status	
NORMAL	79 (73.8)
HYPERTENSIVE	28 (26.2)

Key: n= frequency %= percentage

As shown in the table above, moderate numbers of the participants were newly diagnosed as hypertensive.

The table 6 below draws correlation between physical/anthropometric characteristics, some risk factors and the undiagnosed hypertension.

Table 6: Pearson and Spearman correlation summary showing relationship between undiagnosed HTN and risk factors of HTN

Variables	R	P-value
GENDER	0.113	0.032
AGE	0.251	0.024
BMI	0.208	0.001
OCCUPATIONAL STRESS	-0.079	0.133
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY LEVEL	-0.193	0.001
FAMILY HISTORY OF DM	0.039	0.460
FAMILY HISTORY OF HTN	-0.040	0.441
DIETARY HABITS	0.074	0.158
SMOKING	0.070	0.182

Key: BMI=Body mass index R=correlation coefficient P-value at 0.05

Discussion

The prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension among health care workers in Dutse was found to be 35.4% which is higher than the 27% prevalence reported in Zimbabwe general population [10]. Similar report was documented in an attempt to determine the prevalence of undiagnosed HTN in an emergency department of Imam Hossein Medical and Educational center, Teheren, Iran. The prevalence was found to be 28.6%. Barron *et al*, conducted a similar study among adults aged 45+ years, and found the prevalence of undiagnosed hypertension to be 62% [11] [12].

Das *et al*, reported 24.9% of undiagnosed hypertension in West Bengal, Yadav *et al*, reported 32.2% hypertension from Lucknow in the rural Central India, Kannan *et al*, From eastern India, Hazarika *et al*, reported a prevalence of 33.3% in the age group of 30 years and above among the native population of Assam [13] [14] [15]. While hypertension was 13% in rural adults more than 30 years of age in Jammu, Chow *et al*, reported 27% hypertension in rural adults > 30 years of Andhra Pradesh. This was similar to that reported from industrialized economies [16].

In this study, the prevalence of hypertension was found to increase significantly with increasing age. Similar findings were reported by different researchers in various parts of India. In a north Indian study, they noted that hypertension was highest in the age group 60-69 years (64%). Comparable reports were found from many other countries, Erem *et al*. from Turkey, Wang *et al*. from US and Lim *et al*. from Malaysia noted similar trends [17] [18] [19].

This study shows no significant relationship between dietary habits and HTN. It is in consistent with a report by [10]. In contrast, Reddy *et al*, showed a significant relationship between the prevalence of hypertension and dietary habit [20].

Physical activity level was significantly correlated with hypertension in this study. But it was noted that hypertension is significantly associated with sedentary life style Prevalence of hypertension was significantly more in people who lead a sedentary life style [14] [21] [22] [23] [24] [25]. There was no significant relationship between occupational stress and hypertension, similar finding was reported [26]. Occupational stress, or job strain, resulting from a lack of balance between job demands and job control, is considered one of the frequent factors in the etiology of hypertension in modern society. Stress, with its multifactorial causes, is complex and difficult to analyze at the physiological and psychosocial levels [25] [26].

Family history of hypertension was not significantly associated with hypertension in the current study. Similar finding was reported [14] [26]. But positive association of hypertension with family history was reported [17] [27] [28] [29].

Smoking habit was not significantly associated with hypertension. Divan *et al*. and Yadav *et al*, showed similar findings [14][28]. Others reported no association [21][23][26] [29] [30].

It was noted from this study that hypertension is significantly associated with Body Mass Index. Similar findings were reported [14][17] [21] [22][29] [30] [31].

Conclusion

A moderate prevalence (35.4%) of undiagnosed hypertension was found among health care workers in Dutse, Northwestern Nigeria. Hypertension was found to be associated with Age, BMI, and Physical Activity level.

Recommendation

Health care workers should be encouraged to have routine check-up of their blood pressure so as not to neglect themselves. Awareness should be promoted among healthcare workers on the need for them to participate in more physical activity and weight reduction so as to reduce the impact of the relationship between physical activity, BMI and Hypertension.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.